

Research Topic: *A Comparison Study between the U.K. and Saudi Arabia in Ethical Investment.*

Abstract

The study below conducts an investigation to understand the motivations of ethical investors in the United Kingdom (The UK) with the ethical investors in Saudi Arabia. The study is a desk-top based research conducted with the help of the existing literature and data available from reliable sources. The study endeavours to address three research questions to address the key of the research. The three factors consist of monetary motivation, social motivations, and environmental motivation. The study identified as number of motivations from both the countries under investigation and proceeds to conduct the comparison leading to the conclusions of the study.

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CHAPTER ONE : INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The global corporate world is witnessing the emergence of a new concept called 'ethical investment' based on ethical decision in investment in face of the recent financial crisis (Aktas et al., 2011). Even though this appears to be a recent concept, it has been in existence for a while now (Hill et al., 2007). The earliest trace of ethical investing was witnessed in the attitude of religious institutions suggesting how to make investments (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007). More recently the root of ethical investments are more evident with Islamic banking, where the Quran states what is ethical and what is not (Hussein and Omran, 2005).

It would be worthy to shed some light on the term 'ethical investing'. Basically the term refers to an investment practice based on the integration of social, ethical and environmental dimensions in the process of making investment decisions (Richardson, 2009). Thus, the aim is to extend the financial consideration before making an investment (McLachlan and Gardner, 2004). This can be further elucidated that unlike the traditional approach where the companies that believe in ethical investment go that extra mile to employ the array of investment screen to filter the companies that need to be included or excluded from their portfolio (Bennett, et al., 2005). The screens for these filters predominantly consist of ethical, , corporate governance and social factors (Bennett, et al., 2005). Moreover, this concept also emphasizes on the role of stakeholders to play an active role in the inclusion of more corporate strategies that focus on ethics in business (Friedman and Miles, 2001).

However, the term has witnessed the evolution of the term and contemporary ethical investing is more underpinned on the social and ethical foundations of individual investors (Sparkes, 2002). The world witnessed the rise of contemporary ethical investing in the 1960s when the American Universities started questioning the ethics of the companies involved in war production that eventually evolved into a business philosophy (Renneboog et al., 2008). The process initially started with labour management ethical that further encompassed the environmental dimensions (Richardson, 2009). Currently ethical investment has become a rapidly evolving term where the investors do not limit their concerns on their investment to the returns,

rather they demonstrate increasing concern on the ethical standards employed (Galema et al., 2008). More and more investors now want to invest in companies based on their ethical decision and the level of the concern for the society (Aktas et al., 2011). Similarly contemporary business organisations demonstrate different approach to promote ethics in business management (Allen et al., 2007). Currently the business arena is witnessing a trend where investors tend to invest in company demonstrating higher standards of ethics in their business activities (Dillenburger et al., 2003). This can be explained where earlier the investment decisions were based on the a simple triangle to cover liquidity, returns and risk (Bollen, 2007). However, the more evolved model is now based on the magical square that covers liquidity, risk returns and sustainability as depicted in the diagram below:

**Investor needs in the investment process: Cengiz et al.
(2010)**

1.1 Research Gaps

Currently, the existing literature on ethical investment predominately is from the developed countries consisting of the USA, the UK and Australia that demonstrate notable trends in the area of ethical investments (Bauer et al., 2007). Further, in these countries the culture further promotes the ethics in the behaviour of corporation, with the recent intervention from the government towards more ethical behaviour on part of business organisations (Hussein and Omran, 2005). Similarly many more developed countries have demonstrated an increased participation in ethical investments, as seen in Europe, and Canada (Renneboog et al., 2008). The extant literature review presents evidence on the significant level of investment according to the principles of ethical investment, with a total of \$3.07 trillion in ethical investments

in 2010 (Social Investment Forum, 2010). Europe reports € 5 trillion in ethical investments. Moreover, the extant literature review presents screening methods used in 19 European countries (Hummels and Timmer, 2004). Further, research demonstrates the overview of evolution of ethical investments in the USA, Europe, Canada and Australia where the investors have combined their financial motives with ethical (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). However, the trend is not visibly notable in the developing countries. Therefore, the current research endeavour to address this gap and investigate the situation with ethical investment in the developing countries (Bauer et al., 2006). The research narrows down the focus to compare one developed nation with one developing nation. The researcher chose the UK as the developing country to be compared with Saudi Arabia with focus on the motivations that underpin the decision towards ethical investment. . The key reason for choosing the UK is because of the country of research to fulfil the requirement of the academic project, and Saudi Arabia as the research can make a contribution with the findings and knowledge towards their home country.

Currently, Saudi Arabia has stressed the role of transparency and due diligence in its investment structure, reporting and business process at the same time integrating the social, environmental and corporate governance in its investments (Reutuers, 2017). The nation is witnessing its focus on developing a more prudent approach towards ethical investment based on the principles of transparent structures and strong governance. To elaborate this further, the nation is now focussing its approach beyond robust returns and performance that extends to the investments to benefit their society in compliance with the Shariah and eliminate the any kind of non-transparency in investments. Furthermore, research demonstrates that Shariah compliant portfolios have demonstrated high level of performance in terms of ethical investment. The focus is further to combine ethical investment and principles of Shariah finance to create optimum ethical investment features for investors (Hastings, 2017). With this understanding, the current research endeavours to conduct a comparison study to evaluate the scenario in terms of ethical investment in developed country (the UK) and a developing country (Saudi Arabia). The key aim of the research is to

Conduct A Comparison Study of motivations between the U.K. and Saudi Arabia in Ethical Investment.

Thus, the key aim of the study is to investigate the motivations that explain why individuals and institutions in the UK (a developed nation) chose to engage with ethical investment in comparison to its counterpart Saudi Arabia (a developing nation). To achieve the research aim, the research achieves research objectives as elaborated below:

1. To conduct an investigation of the monetary motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and compare and contrast the same in Saudi Arabia
2. To conduct an investigation of the social motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and compare and contrast the same in Saudi Arabia
3. To conduct an investigation of the environmental motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and compare and contrast the same in Saudi Arabia.

Thus, the study investigates the three dimensions of motivations consisting of monetary, social and environmental to compare and contrast the motivations between the developed and the developing country.

The rest of the thesis is organised as follows:

1. **Chapter Two:** Presents the literature review with focus on the evolution of literature ethical investment over a period of time with emphasis on the critical evaluation of different definitions present in academia (Haigh and Hazelton, 2004). The discussion proceeds to understand how the literature has classified the broad categories of investor groups to understand their motivations for investment decisions based on ethics.
2. **Chapter Three:** This chapter presents the research methodology that helps the researcher to conduct the research.
3. **Chapter Four:** This chapter presents the analysis of the data collected to address the research questions.
4. **Chapter Five:** The chapter proceeds with the discussion on the analysis of the data collected in chapter four and highlights the findings of the research.
5. **Chapter Six:** The discussion proceeds to draw to the conclusion based on the findings with the list of best practices as contribution of the research and discipline. The research ends by presenting the limitations and indicating the scope for future research.

1.2 Research Methodology

The key research approach is secondary research that consists of the collation and summary of the existing research to analyse the scenario of ethical investment in the two countries. The key reason for not including primary research is because of the challenges of accessibility in Saudi Arabia. The research employs a systematic approach to review the articles to gather and assess the data available in research publication and to ensure minimum bias in the study (Bennett et al., 2005). The research will be based on a robust and reliable organisation of evident to ensure reliable findings and conclusion. The main stay of the research is the review and analysis of the peer-review and edited articles, just not restricted to the electronic databases. However, the research extends to the research of a time intensive process of hand search of academic books, journals, conference papers, and on-going and unpublished research process.

CHAPTER TWO : LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Literature Review

The primary aim of this chapter is to present a critical review of the extant literature review on the many dimensions of ethical investments, focussing on the broad overview of ethical investments, motivations of ethical investors and the screening process of ethical investors. The section starts by presenting a background of ethical investment, followed by a broad overview of the terms ethical investment and the current scenario of the discipline.

The contemporary world is witnessing a e trend of ethical investment, also popular by many other names such as social investment, socially responsible investment (SRI), green investment, socially conscious investment or sustainable investment. The key rationale behind this approach of investments is to consider the financial returns, taking into account the social contribution and the positive changes the investment can do (Aktas et al., 2011). Thus, it basically refers to the conscious endeavour towards the social impact created by the investment.

This can be considered as a further extension of the corporate social responsibility that plays an imperative role in the contemporary business era that ensures that the corporation is focusing on the impact of its business operations on consumers, environment, human rights, child-labour, labour protection and similar issues (Fowler and Hope, 2007). Similarly, ethical investment is focuses on the areas of environment, corporate governance, and social justice (Sandberg et al., 2009). Basically ethical investment refers to the concept that encourages the potential investors to decide on specific investment portfolios (Benson and Humphrey, 2008). It basically refers to the practices with the help of screens that ensure the company causes no harm to the planet in any dimensions with its business operations (Pasewark and Riley, 2010). However, the endeavour extends beyond this. The rationale is to encompass more upbeat practices such as community investing, impact investing and shareholder advocacy that is foundation of investment in the current era to guide the potential investors towards responsible investing, rather than just using screening to eliminate the companies that do not fall in the definition of ethical investment portfolios (Renneboog et al., 2009). With this background it would be worthy to cite

the definition of ethical investing before the discussion process to the different sections of the literature in alignment with the research questions.

There are many terms associated with the term ethical investment provided by the extant literature review. Some of them consist of corporate responsible investments, socially responsible investments, and ethical investments (Mill, 2006). The academia and the industry still lacks the universal agreement on the term ethical investments, the discussion endeavour to critically discuss some of the terms and concepts offered by the extant literature review to describe the term ethical investment and understand the motivations behind them (Mackey et al., 2007). This will aid the study to narrow down to the definition to be the most suitable one to lead towards problem formulation and also provide an insights on the history and usage of these terms. The discussion starts by presenting the basic definition of the term fund.

2.1 What is a Fund?

For the purpose of the current study, funds refer to the shares of listed companies in their respective stock exchanges, typically consisting between 50 and 100 companies the portfolio, with the aim of risk minimization by diversification (Lu and Chan, 2012). The focus of the current study is purely on equity funds. The current study does not consider mixed funds.

2.2 DEFINITION of 'Ethical Investing'

Ethical investment predominantly depends on the ethical principles that work as the key filters to selection of portfolios to select. Furthermore, ethical investment also depends on the views of the investors that aid in making the decision to eliminate specific portfolios or industries, such as drugs, alcohol, gambling that potentially cause harm to the society on the whole (Mackey et al., 2007). It would be worthy to highlight the difference between ethical investment and social conscious investment for the purpose of the current study, more often than not the two terms have been used inter-changeably, however, socially conscious investment depends on the predominant set of guidelines to make a decision whether to invest in the portfolio, however ethical investment is in contrast where the decision to invest in a portfolio is dependent on personal choice based on personal preferences, what makes it worthy to

investigate the motivation that underpin ethical investment (Lu and Chan, 2012). This can be further elucidated that ethical investment predominantly equips individuals with the power to allocate their investment with the companies whose values are in alignment with their personal beliefs, views and values, around political, environmental or religious precepts (Lu, and Chan, 2012). It would be imperative to highlight that ethical is not the same as investing with the companies to outperform their competitors (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). This makes it imperative to study the areas for ethical investment where the potential investors want to invest their capital that helps the investors towards the asset allocation plan towards specific portfolios (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007)

2.3 Ethical Investment Background

More often than not, ethical investment is based on the motivation that potentially arises from the religion of an individual, with the aim of eliminating investment in industries that encourage sin in the society. The earliest of ethical investment can be traced back in the USA when in the 18th century Quakers decided not to invest in companies that engage in slave trade (Benson and Humphrey, 2008). In the same era this was further evident in the endeavours of John Wesley, the key founder of Methodism that emphasised on abstaining from investing in industries that cause harm from the chemical plants in the vicinity they operate in (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). Ethical investment further witnessed evolution in the 20th century based on social principles rather than religious principles that guide their ethical investment decisions. This further stretched to political reason during the 60s and 70s in the USA where organisations started to focus on labour rights and equality and refrained from investing in those who did not emphasised on the same (Barnett and Salomon., 2006). One such example was when Americans refrained from investing in companies that supported the war in Vietnam. With the further evolution, ethical investments shifted their focus on the environmental dimensions and ethical investor decided to refrain from investing in companies that did not focus on sustainable and green production methods (Baron, 2001). Thus the evolution has led to the current era, where ethical investors focus on the social, political and environmental dimensions to screen the investment portfolios to be selected (Capelle-Blancard and Monjon. 2012)

2.4 Overview of Ethical Investment

The section endeavours to present a critical overview of the ethical investment, currently happening the world. It is encouraging to note the evolution of the ethical investments in the past few decades. As highlighted earlier, the origins of ethical investment emerged in the USA, in the last 1960s to fulfil religious considerations . However, the industry has witnessed tremendous evolution since then making it a trillion dollar industry in the current era based on radical progressions, specifically in the last decade. Currently, this industry demonstrates a growth rate of approximately 35%, whereas the growth rate witnessed in the conventional investment companies is only about 3%. Currently, USA demonstrates witness for every 1 from 8 dollars US towards ethical investment (USSIF, 2018). The industry has just not witnessed the growth of cash inflow but also continual evolution in the ethical investment products offered by companies. Contemporary organisations have started to realise that role of ethics and ensuring shareholder value in achieving organizational objectives . Secondly, Europe is the second largest market for ethical witness immense growth in the last few decades (Dorfleitner et al., 2012). One of the key reasons for this spectacular growth is based on the factors of integrated climate change provided by the region. Secondly, a majority of growth stems from the investments that been done in the ethical investment bonds, although not in the scope of the current study (Capelle-Blancard and Monjon. 2012). However, even now the majority of the funds in ethical investments are equity funds. The key players for ethical markets in Europe consist of the United Kingdom, France and Netherlands (Bello, 2005). It would be worthy to highlight that in Europe the ethical investment industry is predominantly found by institutional investors that current hold a market share of approximately 92%.

Furthermore, the forecast for the coming is hope to witness a continual growth in ethical investment as part of risk management for both private and institutional investment. Furthermore, the UN has provided a set of guidelines known as Principles for Responsible Investment Initiative (PRI) based on the coordination of investors from all over the world that help in framing best practices that help the ethical investors implement the same towards their ethical investment (Dillenburger et al., 2003). Moreover, in Europe, there have been national regulations that lead to ethical investment, further demanding transparency from institutional investors (Bello, 2005).

Furthermore, the continually increasing coordination between the screening agencies, corporate managers and fund managers has been the key drivers in Europe for the continual growth of ethical investments (Baron, 2001). Moreover, it is also worthy to cite the role of the global economic crisis that result in the increasing distrust from the conventional investments thus paving a path for more ethical investments. This has been further accompanied by the need for social and environmental needs for ethical investments to address the need for sustainable investment even more in the times of global financial crisis (Derwall et al., 2000). The investors are not longer daunted by the fear of inadequate financial performance of their investment, and don't deter them from focussing on the ethical dimensions of investment to address the social and environmental needs (Cummings, 2000). Moreover, Scandinavia is has demonstrated significant growth in terms of ethical investment with the current size of the industry to €435 billion. The key driver for this growth has been the demand from the investors on the companies to address the ethical aspects of investments (Dowell et al., 2000). This makes the Danish, Swedish and Norwegian markets to the key players in the Scandinavia in ethical investments (Dupré et al., 2004). The key capital is from the pensions funds along with the role of government regulations that demand the focus on ethical dimensions in the process of investments to consider the ethical, social and environmental dimensions. Similarly, the Norwegian investment markets focus on the future generations based on sustainable investments, focus on economy and ethical approach. Thus, in Scandinavia, the key players are the Norwegian and Swedish markets. It would also be imperative to highlight the role of screening (discussed in-depth in the later sections) in the success of ethical investment industry in Scandinavia that also presents a positive growth trend in the near future. Moreover, some of the incident happened in the recent times consisting of the oil catastrophe that took place in the Gulf of Mexico, or the incident in Fukushima Japan, the nuclear incident played an imperative role to drive the private investors to demand from accountability and responsibility from the companies in terms of ethics in business (Fowler and. Hope. 2007)

2.5 Motivation For Ethical Investments

The key aim of the study is to understand the motivations of the ethical investors to engage with ethical investment. The aim is achieved by studying the financial, social/ethical and environmental motivations as objectives to address the key aim of the study. The literature review has always found it challenging to accurately measure the motivations that underpin the decision of the ethical investors, the current discipline is witnessing a rapidly increasing surge to study investments based on ethical considerations based on various screening strategies (Sandberg et al., 2009).

Some of the motivations for ethical investment simply are driven by straightforward financial motives, whether the ethical investments can produce a higher yield in compared to conventional investments (Pasewark and Riley, 2010). Moreover, some of the investors seek investment that is in alignment with their ethics, religion and values (Pasewark and Riley, 2010).

The key monetary motivation is primarily to make a smart investment that helps the investors to maximise the return on investment with the help of new and innovative investment processes (Cummings, 2000). Moreover, this approach also emphasises the development of economy by mitigating the risk to the depletion of natural resources (Goss and Roberts, 2011). Lastly, the motivations towards environment, also known as sustainability megatrends that focus on managing resource scarcity, climate change, reducing inequality in the economy in the rapidly evolving business arena (Koellener et al., 2005).

Secondly, looking at the social motivation, it highlights, the emphasis the service of the investment to the society with the help of effective deployment of capital. This motivation can be further elaborated as the employment of investment in any activity that does not cause harm to the society, also extended as a morality, philanthropy and bring the returns on investment with positive contribution to society (Dowell et al., 2000). This is further extended to the contribution to the economic contribution in form of water, land development energy, and health benefits (Dowell et al., 2000). The aim is to strengthen the economy on the principles of sustainability.

It is also worthy to highlight the three motivations are not mutually inter-changeable and is possible for one single investor to demonstrate all the three motivations to

make an ethical investment, for example, the ethical investor that aims to provide service to the society based on the economic imperative many also have interest in understand the social and environmental impact of the investment on the society where it operates. Some of the motivations consist of investing the endeavour of their investment to mitigate the risk to the environment, what are the strategies used to make the optimum use of the scarce resources (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007). These motivation could be the prime factors that drive the decisions of the ethical investors to decide where their investment needs to be employed. This also promotes the interaction of the investors with the similar actors with the policy makers and investment chains to focus on the internationalisation of the social and environment contribution to be evident in their financial statement of the company (Mill, 2006).

Currently, the contemporary world in face of globalisation is facing a strong demand for economic growth, further highlighting the role of responsible investment (ethical investment) further highlighting a need for a sustainable economy as a pressing demand to focus on environment with the long-term perspective. The contemporary investors are aware of the fact that many contemporary business provide goods and services that have not demonstrated appropriate accountability, also resulting in over-use and inefficiency (Goss and Roberts, 2011). This is resulted in a situation where the investors are demanding accountability of the damage caused by the business on the environment, further questioning the impact of business activities on over-fishing, deforestation, and soil erosion (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007). The investors further express their concern over the over use of scarce resource impacting their long-term availability for the future generations further posing a systematic risk to the global economy because of the reliance on nations that are experiencing resource deficit themselves. Furthermore, some of the challenges of the modern day business result in land degradation and pollution that further impact the health of human being and livestock and impact the general well-being (Jacob, 2012). Furthermore, the seas, rivers, land and air have become a dump for business further resulting in more pollution and harm to mankind. The contemporary world is yet to witness the effective intervention of government in controlling the impact of green house emissions by the companies (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007) . Thus, these are some of the key environmental motivations for ethical investors.

Furthermore, one of the motivations tends to be rather a psychological reason towards ethical investment that helps in coping up with the potential slumps and negative performances of the investment. This can be elaborated, the motivation is that individuals want to be true to their moral values, accompanied by the correlated positive feeling to contributing to the community and the environment lowers the feeling of disappointment when the investment performs less than expected (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007) . Moreover, some of the most cited motivations for engaging with ethical investments have been the behaviour of the company towards the social and environmental dimensions. However, it is worthy to highlight that these investors care equally for the financial performance of the investment as much do the investors with non-ethical investments do. Thus, both the conventional investors and ethical investors pay equal importance to financial returns expected on the investment.

2.6 Kinds of Ethical Investment Funds

This section discusses the different categories of ethical investment funds to help in understanding the motivations of the ethical funds better in the subsequent sections. The first criterion is “Best-in-industry” Funds. As the name suggests, these are the funds that work as role model in the industry, based on their performance and behaviour in its industry (Dowell et al., 2000).

Secondly, voice funds, this criteria decides to invest in companies with aim of changing their behaviour towards ethical investment for the better. Predominantly, the shareholders play an imperative role in reshaping the resolutions and conducts of the company in an idealist way (Kempf and Osthoff, 2007) . Thus, this approach is based on shareholder activism. This is done in two ways, either with the shareholders speaking in the meetings to change the resolutions and the second category is shareholder lobbyist funds where the shareholders buy enough number of shares to have the power and influence to change the behaviour of the companies towards ethical investment (Fowler and. Hope, 2007).

Lastly, the third criterion is Sustainable Growth Funds, that work on the principles of cleaner production principles and principles eco efficiencies that work towards sustainable development of the economy it is working in (Jacob, 2012). The decision is taken based on the future performance and analysis of the strengths, weakness,

opportunities and threats in terms of social, political, environmental and technological dimensions (Renneboog, et al., 2008). The criterion helps the portfolio manager to select the best performing company in dimensions of sustainability as a long-term performer.

2.7 Ethical Investment: Screening Strategies

As the name indicates, screening refers to the criteria that ethical investors apply to the investment portfolio to filter the securities and portfolios (Kinder and Domini, 1997). The extant literature review sheds light on two categories of screens, namely, positive and negative. Renneboog et al., (2008) further emphasis that more often than not, ethical investors employ combination of strategies to screen the companies for the investment of their capital. For example, one screen provided by the church that suggests to refrain from the ‘sin stocks’, consisting of tobacco, gambling, alcohol (Cowton, 1998). This approach of screening has been termed as negative screening by the extant literature review. Similarly, there is a broad array of negative ethical investment screens such as gambling, alcohol, tobacco, military contracting, nuclear power (Kinder and Domini, 1997).

Similarly, the focus on environment, quality, customer service, employee rights, corporate social responsibility and cultural diversity are also perceived as negative screens (Camey, 1994). This can be further extended to the repressive government organisations that are considered as negative screens for ethical investors. So basically, these factors that help in understanding the negative ethical investment screens (motivations) to understand why the investors exclude certain investment portfolios in their selection process (Atkas et al, 2011). However this approach has been criticized by scholars on the reliability of the negative ethical screens (Fowler and Hope, 2007). The scholars further argue that is the need to focus on the positive elements to be put in place while screening the investment portfolios. The researchers further argue for the need to employ explicit codes as screens to filter investment portfolios rather than rely on the social, religious, political beliefs, values and attitudes to justify an ethical investment (Chapple and Moon, 2005).

Further, it would also be worthy to highlight one of the greatest challenges while screening portfolios towards ethical investments is selecting the companies to be excluded. This can be elucidated with an example, looking into the screening of military contracts, some ethical investors refrain from all the companies involved with arms and ammunition business, however some refrain from investing only those companies that are either involved or manufacturing or distribution of arms (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). Similarly, there are instances where individuals refrain from investing only in subsidiaries involved with production of arms and ammunition whereas some refrain from investing in companies with significant interest in the military contract (Bugg-Levine and Emerson, 2011) .

Further, investigating into the second dimensions of screening ethical investments the positive way. This criterion defines the specific standards for the investment portfolio to meet for the ethical investors to invest their capital in companies that meet these standards (Fowler and Hope, 2007). However, researchers have criticised this approach of ethical screening because the basic definition of ethical investment relies on the principle of voluntary choice. However, it is also imperative to shed light on the hidden motives of many investors that use the guise of ethical investment to basically support unethical practices (Chapple and Moon, 2005). Moreover, looking back at the time when the ethical investments first came to surface the key motivations were morality, accountability and responsibility towards the world on a broad level, however, currently ethical investment is more concerned with increased profitability or to reduce risk. This potentially could explain the reasons for the increased advocacy for governmental regulation to standardized the norms for ethical investment (Bugg-Levine and Emerson, 2011). Moreover, the traditional approach of negative and positive ethical screens have also resulted to a new approach called mixed screening based on a two stage approach that initiates with native screening followed by positive screening along with the element of trade off approach that helps in producing a broad score to rate the companies under the principles of ethical investment (Benson and Humphrey, 2008). Moreover, the more evolved approach apart from the negative and positive screening is the best-in-class approach that provides a list of the companies in the specific industry where some companies are chose as role model of ethical investment for other players in the industry (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). This structure has been criticized as been good but not clean.

Furthermore, the evolution of the positive screen has been known as the activist approach, one of the key approaches is shareholder activism. As the name indicates the shareholders of the company play an imperative role to bring about a positive change based on the understanding of the rights, privileges, issues and development by exercising their voting rights in the company meetings (Benson and Humphrey, 2008). Furthermore, the next screening approach is community development investing where the investors trade-off some of their profits towards individuals who else would have not access to the same based on the conventional channels (Fowler and Hope, 2007). This process is carried with the help of charity contributions, volunteer programs, or engaging in charitable contributions. However, this has been argued upon by researchers that this should not be considered a part of ethical investment rather an extension of social direct investment (Chapple and Moon, 2005). The intention of the two processes can be explained where ethical investments are undertaken for profitability, social direct investment are undertaken for social development. However, researchers further argue it would be worthwhile to rather focus on the idea of investment to create a positive impact on social and environmental dimensions rather wasting the resources on defining the difference between ethical investment and social direct investment (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). The aim here to create a positive impact on the process of optimization of financial returns (Bugg-Levine and Emerson, 2011). This approach of investment is gaining more and more significance in the domain of ethical investment

Moreover, ethical investors are driven by the motivation to avoid companies that cause harm to the world in the dimensions of environment, social factors and political factors. At the same time many ethical investors want to create a positive impact on the society, or perhaps some of the ethical investors just want to invest in ethically clean investments. Furthermore, some of the investors indicate their motivation towards ethical investment based on moving away from the evils of globalisation and capitalism (Chapple and Moon, 2005). The trend is becoming more and more evident amongst the investors where only a few niche investors who were powerful engaged in ethical practices, currently there has been witness of tremendous growth in the last few years making it an imperative part of the mainstream investment discipline (Atkas et al, 2011). Moreover, it is encouraging to see the similar trend that started with private investors progress to institutional investors engaging with ethical investment. Moreover, many institutional investors have made explicit endeavours to

promote the social, environmental and good corporate governance into consideration before making their investment decisions (Benson and Humphrey, 2008)

However, it would be worthy to cite the differences in the motivation of the private investors and institutional investors. With institutional investor the key objective is the maximization of shareholder value (Atkas et al, 2011). Moreover, just not the investors but also the companies that are being screened for ethical investments demonstrate more and more endeavours to conduct their business operations based on ethical practices (Barnea and Rubin, 2010). It would be safe to imply from this that the companies that tend to be ethical potentially are being penalised by the capital market because the investors moving towards companies who meet their ethical requirements, making them pay a higher cost of capital because of the financing of the capital by themselves. Thus, this provides motivation to the companies themselves to engage with ethical practices. Research also demonstrates that ethical investment has forced companies to align their behaviour with that of the ethical business practices (Fowler and Hope, 2007).

Thus, one of the motivations of engaging in ethical investments is to eliminate the evil practices from the free market economy based on the business ethics. In simple words, it could mean the endeavours of the ethical investors to invest in a free market economy where one of the key motivations is to eliminate or undermine specific evils of the free market economy, or secondly to promote the inculcation of certain practices that indicate the normative perspective of the ethical investors (Benson and Humphrey, 2008). Thus, the analysis can indicate the key motivation for the potential investors to engage with ethical investment, financial motivations, non-financial motivations and motivations to bring about a social change (Chapple and Moon, 2005). The lists of motivations identified are not comprehensive or exhaustive and there is always a trade-off to explain the behaviour patterns of ethical investors. Where on one hand, the ethical investors experience a maximised total utility based on small ethical investment, also known as the fun of participation model. Moreover, psychic returns can explain the motivations that lead to the increase in the happiness of ethical investors (Barnea and Rubin, 2010).

Thus, the motivations cited by the private investors and institutional investors to engage with ethical investments is complex and diverse, and the extant literature review is yet to make a comprehensive list of the motivations that drives individuals

and institutions towards screening companies towards ethical investments (Chapple and Moon, 2005)

CHAPTER THREE : RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Research Methodology

Technology has made it up possible to amass vast amount of data that have been collected earlier, compiled and archived for some other reason, however, is accessible for research (Andrews et al., 2012). This has resulted in a trend in research where researchers are utilizing the existing data to conduct further investigation, known as secondary data analysis (Maxwell, 2012). This approach equips the researcher with flexibility as the process just involved collecting and analyzing secondary data (Easton, 2010).

The study is based on the assumption that the secondary data analysis is the most appropriate approach to utilize it in the process of enquiry to address the research questions with a systematic procedure of enquiry (Magee, et al., 2006). Thus, the current research is based on collecting secondary data to addresses the research questions (Boslaugh, 2007). With this background, the current chapter discusses the research methodologies.

3.1 Research Design

The key aim defining a research design in study is to provide an outline on how the research will be conducted with a logical approach including the many dimensions of research (Saunders et al., 2009). The research design works as blue print that helps the researcher to stick to the original aim and objectives of the study (Yin, 2003). The research design also describes the data collection and data analysis approach (Monte, 2005). Thus, it is an opportunity provided to the research to be articulate on the data required to address the research questions, starting from the data collection process and data collection sources to defining the strategies to analyse data to successfully answer the research questions (Sapsford and Jupp, 1996). The research design helps the researcher to ensure the smooth and efficient data collection in a pragmatic manner, being prepared for the different challenges that will come in the way (Smith et al., 2011). Moreover, one of the key reasons for defining the research methodology is to clearly define the key goals of investigations and choose the mode of enquiry to be either descriptive, exploratory, or evaluation (Robson, 2002)

The extant literature review presents a broad range of frameworks that helps the research to adapt to a research design. One of the popular frameworks is the ‘Onion’ provided by Saunders et al. (2012). The current implements the ‘onion’ to define the research methodology for the current study. The diagram below presents the different components discussed individually to reflect the research design for the current study.

Figure 3.1: Research Onion Framework :Source: Saunders & Lewis (2012)

3.2 Research Philosophy

The key aim of defining the research philosophy is to define the sources of data will be employed that will eventually lead to the development of data (Adams and Schvaneveldt, 1991). It is worthy to highlight that the process of knowledge development even though appears to be a challenging process, nonetheless, defining the process aids the researcher with complete engagement to address the research objectives (Kiecolt and Nathan, 1985). Furthermore, it is in this step the researcher define the requirement of the primary or secondary data that will help in addressing the research questions (Clarke and Cossette, 2000). This also aids the researcher to define the beliefs and assumptions that underpin the current investigation (Dale et al., 1988). This can be explained with further reference to the ‘Onion’ framework where the first layers of the framework is to define the philosophy (Baker, 1990)

Similarly, the philosophy helps in defining the fundamental and beliefs that underpin the different stages of conducting the research that help in developing knowledge (Stewart and Kamins,1993). In this case the key data is secondary in nature, however, the aim is to develop new knowledge based on the comparison of two countries bearing in mind, the fundamental comparison is to study a developed and a developing country (Remenyi et al., 1998). Moreover, defining the underlying beliefs and assumptions helps the research to define the next step of research strategy (Creswell, 2009)

The extant literature review provides four options to choose from the research philosophy , consisting of positivism, realism, pragmatism, and interpretivism (Neergaard and Ulhoi, 2007). More often than not the challenge is to choose between positivism and interpretism, however with many contemporary studies pragmatism and realism have demonstrated immense success (Malhotra and Birks, 2003).

Moreover, considering from the perspective of the current student, there is also an element of phenomenology, because the study aims to study the phenomenon of ethical investment and study the attitude of the investors from two countries (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2002). Thus, the study aims to provide an overview of the situation in the two countries but understanding the motivation of ethical investors (Hakim, 1982). Potentially, this approach will help the to analyse the secondary data with precision (Heaton, 2008).

Furthermore, phenomenology can be defined to be descriptive, heuristic and interpretative, and the aim of the current study is to interpret the role of ethical investments in the two countries based on the secondary data, therefore the most appropriate would be interpretative phenomenology (Doolan and Froelicher, 2009) Further, progressing to data analysis, this approach aids the researcher to analyse the secondary data with the help of reduction, analysis, intuition and description (Adams and Schvaneveldt, 1991). This particular helps the research in the process of data analysis from different resources both online and offline (Andrews et al., 2012). This approach would help the researcher to conduct an in-depth investigation (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002).

The second step consist of intuiting that aid the study to analyse the data in context of the situation, specially in this case because the study is in context of a developed and a developing country (Yin, 2003). The last step helps the researcher to describe the data analysis in context of the developed and developing countries.

3.3 Time horizon

Time horizon is the core of Saunders Onion frameworks that helps in defining the timeframe for which the research is carried out. There are two time-frames consisting of longitudinal and cross-section (Creswell, 2009). A longitudinal study helps the researcher to carry on with a study over a period of time to study the evolution of a phenomenon, mainly combined with an observational approach (Baker, 1990). However, the aim of cross-sectional research to address a specific question or study a phenomena in the same point of time. This particularly suits the current study, therefore the time-frame for the current study is cross-section, considering the time frame available for the university project an the resources allocated for secondary data collection. Moreover, the current study does not require the data to be collected over a period of time, the data is collected from the existing sources as part of secondary data collection. More often than not studies conduct a cross-section time frame. The current study could have been a longitudinal since it involve archival research, however, the study needs to be completed in accordance with the university deadline.

3.4 Desk Research Approach

This approach is also known as secondary research approach as the key aim of this approach to collate, summarize and produce a synthesis of the existing research rather than collecting data with any of the primary research approaches (Easton, 2010) . The current study analyses the existing data on ethical investment to compare the situation between the two countries with the aim of studying a developed and a developing country. Even though the secondary data comes in an already analysed form, the current study will take a step forward and analyse with a comparative approach (Dale et al., 1988).

As the name indicates, the data is collected sitting at a desk. To elaborate this further, the research involves collecting data from the existing resources to address the research questions (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002). Clearly, the cost involved with this approach is minimum and allows the researcher to focus only on collecting data as there is no field world involved. Currently, most of the existing data is available online and thus, with minimum effort it would be possible to collect the existing data on ethical investment in both the countries (Saunders et al., 2009). Although it would be worthy of cite here that the data available in Saudi is limited as compared to the data available for the UK, as the concept of ethical investment is yet evolving in Saudi Arabia. However, this has been one of the key research gaps that current study endeavours to investigate and potentially take the motivations of the West to the East. Desk research predominantly refers to collecting data from the current sources and for the purpose of the current research will employ both the internal desk research approach and external desk research approach (Boslaugh, 2007). The secondary research for the current research consists of collecting data from academic books (mainly for the theory), academic journals, books, periodicals, databases, index, Internet, market research, Government publication, and newspapers (Doolan and Froelicher, 2009). The secondary data is collected based on the approach of systematic review with the help of meta analytic statistical techniques. However, the research has also taken into account the views of the realists along with the meta narrative reviews in the form of reports and publications (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2002).

Moreover, with reference to the current study, its helps in addressing the specific issues under investigation and analyse the specific issues within the boundaries of the research question. This approach would further aid in emphasizing the definite units of investigation (Sapsford and Jupp, 1996). The key research approach is to collect secondary data and analyse it comparison a developed and developing nation. Moreover, the secondary data will consist of both qualitative and quantitative data that consists of analysis, statistics, tables, facts and figures (Yin, 2002). This approach is most appropriate for to address the current research questions because it aids the research to understand the relationship and inter-dependencies between the different elements of ethical investment that help in conducting the comparison between the developed and the developing nation (Stewart and Kamins, 1993). This approach

predominantly is analytical and interpretative, along with the element of realism to focus on the in-depth analysis to conduct the comparative study to present the comparison based on the overall findings (Yin, 2002).

One of the key aims of the choosing this strategy because there exist research gap to study ethical investments, specifically in the developed nations. Moreover there has been no study conducted with comparative approach. The aim is to take the lesson from the success of ethical investment to the east to promote an environment in the country towards ethical investments (Yin, 2002). This approach will further help in drawing definite conclusions with extreme caution. Thus, the research is carried out with secondary data underpinned with the literature review and include the online source to ensure an interactive research collection methods (Robson, 2002)

The data has been collected from the existing industry reports to understand the role of ethical investment (Smith et al., 2011) . Similarly, data has been collected from government website, archives to ensure that data has been collected from all the possible dimensions. However, one challenge that has been encountered in the process is ensuring the reliability of the data collected Remenyi et al., 1998). Even though it would be a challenge to establish the findings on its own, it would still be useful to provide a reliable comparison between the two countries (Smith et al., 2011)

3.5 Analysis Secondary Data

In the process of collecting secondary, the research questions play an imperative role in guiding the researcher towards the analysis of the secondary data. The current research conducts a comparative study between two countries (Magee, et al., 2006). Even though, it was possible to collect vast secondary data with the help of broad range of resources, one of the challenges for data collection has been understanding the attitudes, norms, and styles of the people who engage in ethical investments (Maxwell, 2012). This is one of the key challenges of the study, that it is difficult to gather primary data, especially from Saudi Arabia, hence the reliance on secondary data. However, conducting the study is not free from its limitations. Some of the key challenges consist of the data collected to be outdated, biased or obtained improperly. However, the researcher was predominantly responsible to identify the data that helps in addressing the research questions (Malhotra and Birks, 2003)

3.6 Data Validation

The researcher ensured the validity of the secondary analysis by spending significant amount of time to ensure the origin of the data sets (Neergaard and Ulhøi, 2007). The researcher kept a record of the following in the table format.

1. The purpose for which every piece of material was collected.
2. The specific methods that was used to collect the same.
3. The information on the population under investigation and just like data ensure the validity of the same captured.
4. The credibility of the source from where the data was collected.
5. The limitations of the data set, indicating the data collected and presented.
6. The political and historic circumstance surrounding to study the creation and collection of the datasets.

This helps the researcher to prepare for the analysis of the secondary data collected. One of the important considerations is on the process of categorizing and coding the data that would an imperative role in ensuring the analysis of the secondary data analysis (Kiecolt and Nathan, 1985). The researcher also made endeavors to adapt and adjust the data before proceeding to the data analysis (Glaser, 1963). It has been far more easy to validate the quantitative data, identify the biases, social context, gaps and similar issues (Hakim, 1982). However, analyzing the quantitative data was the most challenging part and define how the data was collected , why certain data was left out and more specifically providing justification for the tools used to collect secondary data. With this understanding, underpinned by the literature review discussed above, the study developed the research questions to address the key aim of the question (Heaton, 2008).

3.7 Research Questions

The research aims at understanding the motivations that underline the ethical investors in the UK as a developed country and Saudi Arabia as the developing nation. This is done in four dimensions where the key research aim is addressed with

the help of investigation in the monetary motivation, social motivations, and environmental motivations. The analysis of the same will lead to the development of the best practice guideline to foster and encourage the culture and environment of ethical investment in both the countries. To achieve this, the study endeavors to answer the following research question.

1. What are the monetary motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and in Saudi Arabia?
2. What are the social motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and in Saudi Arabia?
3. What are the environmental motivations of investors of ethical investment in the UK and in Saudi Arabia?

3.8 Conclusion

Drawing to the end of the conclusion, the chapter describes the research methodology to address the key aim and objectives of the current study. The key approach selected as research methodology has been collecting and analyzing the secondary data and endeavor to create new knowledge in form of the best practice guidelines (Heaton 2008).

Even though the key research method is based on secondary data collection the research endeavor the body of knowledge by providing a comparative perspective between the developed and the developing country. The research has endeavored to collect high quality secondary data and employ its potential value to gain knowledge and provide insight in the broad range of dimensions involves in ethical investments utilizing the secondary data analysis approach, conducted based on a systematic process that acknowledge the challenges of using secondary data, even though an endeavor has been make systematic and accurate analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR : DATA ANALYSIS

4.0 Data Analysis

This chapter presents the analysis of the data collected from the extant literature review with an endeavour to understand the motivations of ethical investments in the UK and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

4.1 Motivations For Ethical Investments in the United Kingdom

It is encouraging to witness the focus on sustainability and ethics as a part of the contemporary citizens in the UK (EDHEC, 2010) . It is further encouraging to witness the focus on ethical investment as a discrete and identify behaviour of the investors in the financial markets with highlight on the ethical concerns of the society and the environment (Williams and Conley, 2007) . There is a continual growth in the trust funds that depict immense success because of the growth of demand for ethical investments. This also demonstrates the future scope for ethical investments in the UK based on the demands of the investors (Eurosif, 2012). The nation is also witnessing the growth of the ethical funds by open-ended investment companies because the investors have demonstrated a strong inclination only to purchase shares and bonds from companies focussing on fulfilling their social, moral and environmental responsibility (EDHEC, 2010).

Further, looking into the situation in the UK, traditionally investors considered ethical investment to be associated with ‘green investments’ and focus on the environment, predominantly in the renewable energy sector (Webley et al., 2001). However, one of the key hindrances in the process is the dependence on subsidies that tends to be significantly susceptible to the fluctuations in the government policy. Moreover on the positive note, the motivation for ethical investment in the UK is more than the focus on the environment (EDHEC, 2010). The trend as evident, in case of the

investors in the UK is towards the use of ethical screens and avoid the investments in stocks that is considered unethical and has demonstrated significant success in the recent times, especially in the domain of the volatile resources sector.

Moreover, on a positive note, it is worthy to highlight that the investors have extended the definition of ethical investments beyond the concept of the dodgy and vice stocks such as investment in tobacco, fossil fuels, alcohol and arms and ammunition sector. There is further inclination towards a more proactive approach with new concept known as impact investment (Webley et al., 2001). This can be further elaborated as the endeavour of the companies to join in the investors to just not generate profits, rather to work together to actively do good. More and more investors in the UK are now demonstrating the endeavour to invest in the right thing (Eurosif, 2012). However, the study also found that that there is a broad range of interpretation of the term ethical investment and there has been a challenge in clearly defining the term ethical investments (Williams, 2007). Some of the motivations that have been evident in the behaviour of the investors in the UK consist of clean green investments, sustainability, ethical, and responsible investments (EDHEC, 2010).

The nation has witnessed an increase of 11% across the 196 ethical and sustainable funds in the last 4 months with a soaring £10 billion to an enormous £96billion with the help of 3D investing and investing with Good With Money (Jobson, 2017) . More prominently the funds selected by the ethical investors in the United Kingdom that are clearly categorise into nine themes focussed on the social and environmental factors consisting of sustainable infrastructure and transport, resource efficiency, healthcare and education (Jobson, 2017) .

The same motivations are evident in endeavours of the portfolio manager that seek out to work actively with the corporations to provide solutions on the broad range of environmental and social solutions to outperform the expectation of the ethical investors (Webley et al., 2001). Moreover, the literature also highlights the endeavours of the investors to study the focus of the corporations on the ethical dimensions in their annual reports to study the details of the positive impact of the company on the environment (Williams, 2007). This can be elaborated in the statistics where in 2016, for every £1 million that was invested by the investors in the UK, it resulted in the generation of the 1200 MWh that equalled the sum total of the energy usage to the energy consumption of nearly 60 UK households (Jobson, 2017).

This has also helped the nation to eliminate 1600 tonnes of CO₂ carbon emissions that can be compared to over 300 cars off the British road annually (Jobson, 2017).

However, the investors in the UK faced a hindrance as result of the perceived lack of support from the government to tackle the issues surrounding, pollution and exploitation that demands immediate action. Thus, from this it could be implied that one of the motivations of the investors in the UK is to fulfill the inadequately attended (EDHEC, 2010) . However, historically, the investors in the UK demonstrate green investments and ethical investments to be in a psychological conflict with each, where one focuses on doing the right investment, whereas the second demands the highest possible return on their investment. However, the contemporary investors in the UK, no longer tend to demonstrate this conflict and rather depict a clarity on their visions on ethical investments (Eurosif, 2012). However, the challenge still remains where the investors face a moral conflict in deciding whether to invest in ethical investments or green investment, in the recent time there is an inclination towards green investments in the recent years, that also has become the underlying principle for the investors in the UK to invest ethically (Webley et al., 2001). The key principle that defines ethical investment is sharing of responsibility in terms of ethics in business, by both the investors and the companies (Williams, 2007). It is encouraging to see that many organization have ingrained this approach where the management and the investors work together with an endeavour to be ethical in their business (EDHEC, 2010) .

However, currently the nation is facing a demand for the sustainability and energy efficient markets to create new investment opportunities in a broad dimension of sectors. Arguably this one of the key reasons that explains the gradual soaring of the open-ended funds in the nations, approximately by over 100 per cent. However, there is still a clear need to understand the underlying motivations, predominantly being the protection of the scarce environmental resources (Eurosif, 2012).

Furthermore, investigating the situation from the perspective of the government, the key motivations for ethical investment is to address the issues of resource scarcity to meet the growth of the continually growing demand for development of sustainable infrastructure that will not fade away in the near future (EDHEC, 2010). Moreover, it would be worthy to highlight the role of the political situation that demand the company to work in alignment with the environmental policies to in place in the

process of running their business (Cummings and Hehenberger, 2010) . The nation has witnessed the immense growth in the role of governance to analyse the development of the green and sustainable investment in the last 15 years. To ensure this the government has ensure fines and regulations, specifically to address the issues with climate change that have pushed the contemporary organizations to continually innovation new technologies and practices toward energy efficiency and reduce their impact because of carbon emissions (Eurosif, 2012). Furthermore, the government has also encourage ethical practices with the help of tax breaks and subsidies. This has rather played an imperative role in dramatically increasing the number of companies that further encourage ethical investments. Furthermore, the nation has witnessed a growth in the number of renewable energy investment opportunities along with the funds that promote the same idea and principles as evident in the case of Renewable Obligation Certificates (ROC). Furthermore, the Ofgem plays the role of the regulator for the UK gas and electricity sector where the government has promoted ethical business practices with the help of incentives. This has helped the nation to achieve its carbon reduction objectives by 15% of the total energy consumption. Before the year 2020. Moreover there is witness on many of the renewable energy investments corporation and trusts that ensure their ethical practices with the help of Telney Best invest buying rate that included Foresight solar Fund (FSFL), The Renewable Infrastructure Group (TRIG), and the Greencoat UK Wind (UKW) with the top most rating in the domain of ethical investments.

Furthermore, the motivation indicated by the ethical investors in the UK consisted of focussing on the environmental policies of the government to ensure the geopolitical and economic and the geopolitical climate that demonstrates continual growth towards the green sector (EDHEC, 2010) . There is always an argument from the ethical investors on whether it is the job of the government or the investors to ensure ethical practices by corporation. However, one of the key motivations identified is the science that underpins the climate change and how the human activities has resulted in the impact on the climate and remains to be a volatile domain for the ethical investors (Mercer, 2009).

To draw to an end, the key themes identified for ethical investments in the UK has been ethical, green and sustainability as a society on the whole in the last ten years.

this has also helped the nation to push the towards the focus on ethics and demands a change in their business operations.

4.2 Motivations to Analyse Ethical Investment in Saudi Arabia

While financial investments have ethics seem to be mutually exclusive in Saudi Arabia, current the nation demonstrate ethics as one of the key elements in the investment domain (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). Moreover, the focus of the nation is on the role of religious belief and faith that encourage ethical investment practices for investors who thinking beyond profits based on their investment, however acknowledge their moral duties that go beyond seeking wealth and accumulation from their financial investments (Robsin, 2017b).

Further, investigating the motivations of the investors in Saudi Arabia, the extant literature review indicates some of the reasons why investors chose for ethical investment (Bloomberg, 2018). It would be worthy to highlight some of the trends based on Islamic banking and Shariah law that motivated the investors to make a decision (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). The literature review indicates two key areas of investment for the investors in Saudi Arabia consist of screening that help the investors to exclude the investment in the industries that is considered harmful by Islam consisting of tobacco, alcohol and gambling. Secondly, the investors chose to invest ethical to adhere to the Islamic laws with the motivation of green finance that helps it distinguish from the non-ethical investors (Vizciano, 2017). It is also worthy to highlight that the role of ethics is evident in the Islamic faith even since the 7th century as visible in the focus on the societal responsibility and concepts of welfare and pension that make the Five Pillars of Islam religion (Robsin, 2017b).

The nation also demonstrates growing interest towards the role played by ethics and socially responsible investment, at the same time the continually growing interest in Islamic banking and ethics investment. As seen in the principles of Islamic Finance, the key objective remain to establish justice and eliminate the exploitation of business transaction (Robsin, 2017b) . Thus, one of the key motivations identified in Saudi Arabia is to eliminate, unjustified, illegal, transactions that demonstrate excessive risk

or speculation. Thus, the literature demonstrates that many of the investment decisions are based on Islamic Finance that help the investors to invest responsibly and ethically (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004).

Furthermore, the investigations indicate one of the motivations toward ethical investments to expand national relationship globally by demonstrating the awareness toward responsible investment (Vizciano, 2017). Further, the decision towards ethical investments help the investments to focus on their investment decisions with due diligence and transparency focused on investment structures at the same time integrate their decision with the social, environmental, and governance criteria for the overall benefit of the economy (CMA,2017) . It would be worthy to cite the movement called Sedco that depict the endeavours towards ethical investment with focus on green investing, and make highlight the role of ethical investment with the help of Islamic finance appeal, as green finance is becoming is more and more important in appeal in to a wider mass and encourage the role of ethical investment in Saudi Arabia (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004).

Thus, the investors in Saudi Arabia are increasingly employing the principles of Islamic Banking towards ethical, responsible and sustainable development objective in environmental projects (CFA, 2018). Moreover, in the same context some of the objectives identified were elimination of poverty, improving social inequality and the use of impact investing with financial exclusion (IFC, 2018) . Further, the impact investments help the investors to chose value based investment structure that helps the investors to associate themselves with key moral purpose based on the principle of continually engagement in value based engagements that also are the underpinning principle of Islamic Finance (Robsin, 2017b) . Thus, the principles of ethical finance play a significant role to encourage the investors in Saudi Arabia towards ethical investments (Vizciano, 2017). This is also evident in the embraced approach of green Sukuk that helps the business to invest in clean and energy efficient objective for the nation. Apart from the decision to invest in environment conscious portfolio, the investors in Saudi Arabia focus on investing in projects that focus on alleviating global property and reducing inequality of income and power in their economy (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004).

Thus, with the investors in Saudi Arabia the key motivation consist of environmental, socially responsible and ethical values in the investment domain that more often than not emerge from the deep rooted Islamic beliefs, principles, jurisprudence and theology (Saudi Gazette, 2018). These motivations are further extended to motivation of ethical investments towards growth as seen in the ethical and green and financial products based on the teachings of Islamic belief and teaching that motivate the investors towards social and environmental development (Robsin, 2017b) .

However, the extant literature review also presents arguments that it is imperative not to confused the Shariah laws with ethical strategies, the two of them go together hand in hand and should not be considered to be mutually exclusive (Jabri, 2018). The literature further presents witness on the motivation of the investors to invest in projects to make profits while have a purpose towards the society and the environment (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). Thus, the motivations identified here state that social environmental and governance towards ethical investments, with sustainability and simply ethical as one of the motivations (Robsin, 2017b) .

Moreover, the literature presents witness on the potential of Islamic Finance to demonstrate a continual impact on the society when investors make decision in favour of environmental , social and governance factors in the process of investing their money in the projects. This is also evident in the launch of the Prudent Ethical Investing (PEI) from SEDCO capital that promote the integration of the Shariah compliant investment towards ethical investments (Saudi Gazette, 2018). The PEI not only promotes ethical investments but also works as a guide for the investors to make their investment decisions with due diligence and transparency based on their investment processes, structures and reports that integrate the environment, social and governance standards in the investment processes (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). This also helps the investors with a guide to avoid investments in high financial risks and improve the long-term risk adjusted returns (Saudi Gazette, 2018).

Ever since the nation has witnessed a stark soaring in the number of investors to seek out their investment decisions based on the guidelines presented by PEI (Jabri, 2018). Moreover, PEI has encourage international investors to make their investment

decision in Saudi Arabia and select from its over 14 SEDCO Shariah compliant investment strategies the S because of the exceptionally strong platforms offered by the Shariah compliant portfolios (Saudi Gazette, 2018).

Moreover, yet another witness of ethical practices in investment in Saudi Arabia was evident in the rapid expansion of the Green Finance in the investment industry because of the technological breakthroughs and government intervention with the environment friendly and energy alternative solutions (Jabri, 2018). Moreover, the investors depict their investment decision to tap the climate related opportunities and similarly mitigate the risks to demonstrate the shift towards clean energy, this has encouraged the shifts in investment towards projects that promote the use of clean energy (Robsin, 2017b). These investment decision provide the environmental benefits to the investors of Saudi Arabia and leads to the broader context of sustainable and environmental development of the country. This is evident in the investment of nearly \$23 trillion funds that were based on ethical decision in 2016 and significant increase from \$18 trillion in 2014 (Jabri, 2018) . It would also be worthy to highlight that the younger generation in the nation seems to participate more in compared to the older traditional investment in ethical investment based on sustainable objectives. One of the factors that needs to be highlighted is that more often than not ethical investment cost more as compared than the traditional investment, and this could be one of the key deterrents towards ethical investors in Saudi Arabia (Saudi Gazette, 2018). However, currently the Government is taking active interest in promoting the concept of ethical investment, along with a watch dog that helps in ensuring the information of the environment endeavours of the company to the potential investors (Robsin, 2017a).The government currently is covering the key industries in the national consisting of transportation, construction, energy, agriculture, forestry and hospitality. This has extended the motivations of the employees to the diversification of their nation from an oil dependent economy towards a more global economy that also depends on its service industries (Saudi Gazette, 2018). The endeavour is also to minimize the waste on the consumption of energy and promote green building regulation to promote energy efficiency. Further, the government is also in the preparation to launch to the green bonds that will help the economy to finance many of the key mega project with more motivation for

private sector investment funds to join the league. The literatures also demonstrate the motivation towards ethical investments to trigger many new technological breakthroughs that helps in creating a sustainable and environmental based for the nation (Robsin, 2017b)

CHAPTER FIVE : FINDINGS

CHAPTER FIVE: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the comparison of the monetary/financial/ profitability motivation of the ethical investors in the UK with that of the ethical investors in Saudi Arabia. Comparing the scenario in the UK with that of Saudi Arabia, there is a clearly evident trend in the UK, where the investors (stakeholders) are working closely with the management to generate profitability based on the principles of ethical investment. Thus, the aim is to still keep generating profits, however the underlying principle is ethics and play a proactive role in doing good as part of business (Eurosif, 2012). Whereas, looking at the scenario in Saudi Arabia, the underlying principles to do business as ethical investors is religion, even though the business aims at generating profits, it is predominantly in alignment with the principle of Islam. One of the example of profitability with ethics in alignment of Islam is the example of Sukuk bonds (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004).

5.1 Comparison of the Monetary Motivations for Ethical Investments between the UK and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

In the UK, the government offers a broad range of incentives, subsidises and tax breaks, this has motivated many corporates to engage in ethical practices in the process of conducting their business. Similarly, the UK is also under the threat of fines and regulations, where contemporary business are forced to implement ethical practices to keep the impact of their business operation in control in terms of carbon emission (Eurosif, 2012). This is seen in the case of Ofgem, where regulators play an imperative role in motivating the UK enterprises to implement and update ethical business practices by corporations. One of the monetary motivations for Saudi Arabia is to eliminate global poverty and minimize inequality of income by conducting ethical business on the principles of Shariah. Further the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has encourage the concept of impact investments where the investors becomes part of the business to work towards achieving profits based on the principles of Islam (Robsin, 2017b). it would be worthy to highlight the aim of ethical investments in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to discourage the ethical investors from investing in high risk investments (Saudi Gazette, 2018). Similarly, agencies such as PEI have

successfully managed to attract overseas investment because their endeavours towards ethical investment based on the principles of Shariah laws. Moreover, even in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the government has been taking encouraging step to motivate the concept of ethical investment. Moreover, the government also endeavours to help the nation to shift its dependence from its oil based economy to a more diversified nation (Saudi Gazette, 2018). Similarly, the government has provided incentives to the companies practicing ethical investment with a broad range of technological breakthroughs in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. One of the motivations for the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is to be part of the global economy, and develop relationship with other developed countries that focus on the principles of ethical investment.

5.2 Comparison of the Social Motivations for Ethical Investments between the UK and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia demonstrates its focus ethical investments that extends beyond achieving profits from their business and investments by defining the moral duties that does good to the society and contribute to the growth and development of the society and local communities. The endeavour is also evident where the ethical investment restrict the investment in harmful industries defined by Islam that produce tobacco and alcohol and make their profitability from activities such as gambling. Islam believes that these industries will do harm to its people. Therefore the ethical investors refrain from investing in these industries. A Similar trend is evident in the UK where they would not invest in industries that produce weapons or encourage wars, or use animal testing. The aim is to invest in companies that do not cause harm to the society and the community where they live. Moreover, in Saudi Arabia, the social motivations consist of encouragement of social justice and elimination of exploitation with the principles of ethical investment in alignment with the principles of Islamic Finance by eliminating illegal transaction, speculation and unjustified investments and act responsibly (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). Thus, the principles of ethical finance play a significant role to encourage the investors in Saudi Arabia towards ethical investments (Vizciano, 2017). This is also evident in the embraced approach of green Sukuk that helps the business to invest in clean and energy efficient objective for the nation. Apart from the decision to invest in

environment conscious portfolio, the investors in Saudi Arabia focus on investing in projects that focus on alleviating global property and reducing inequality of income and power in their economy (Bayt al-Tamwīl al-Kūwaytī, (2004). In Saudi Arabia, the aim is to invest in companies that allow the investors to earn profit however with focus on contribution to the society the with investments and profitability. Further one of the motivations of Saudi Arabia is to adhere to the governance of the country in favour of social and governance factors, seen in the endeavours of SEDCO that integrates ethical investments with the principles of Sariah and Islamic Finance (Saudi Gazette, 2018).

5.3 Comparison of Motivations For Environmental Ethical Investments in the United Kingdom with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

After discussing the financial and social motivations the discussion now proceeds to compare the environmental motivations of the two countries towards ethical investment. Both countries seem to have strong motivations to make ethical investments because of environmental motivation, more clear and strong. One of the clear environmental motivation in both the countries is green investments where both the countries endeavour that the business results in less impact on the economy because of the business operations. Moreover, both the countries focus on investment in specific industries, such as renewable energy to focus more concerns over the protection the environment. Both the countries demonstrate their motivation towards to create sustainable and energy efficient markets and sustainable infrastructure (Cummings and Hehenberger, 2010) .

CHAPTER SIX : CONCLUSION

6.0 CONCLUSION

The study draws to a conclusion. The key aim of the study was to understand the motivation of the ethical investors in the UK and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study endeavoured to address three research questions:

1. What were the monetary motivations of the investors in the UK and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?
2. What were the social motivations of the investors in the UK and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?
3. What were the environmental motivations of the investors in the UK and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?

With the help of the findings as discussed in the earlier chapter the discussion now draws to a conclusion by addressing the three research questions. The findings found both the countries found support and encouragement from the government towards ethical investments, however, the support has not been adequate and the government from both the countries has used both positive and negative strategies to motivate the businesses and citizens towards ethical investments. Thus, in the process to address the monetary benefits some of the motivations identified were to work with the attitude of doing good and the same time earn profits. Secondly the motivations were to access the incentives and subsidiaries offered by the government and also be in alignment with the laws and regulations.

Secondly, both the countries demonstrate their motivation for social benefits to contribute to the society with their business activities and business investments. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has a special focus on the development of their community in alignment with the principle of Shariah laws and Islamic banking. The nation also endeavours to become part of the global community and help the nation minimize its

dependence on the oil sector and become a more diversified country with focus on other countries.

Lastly, investigating the environmental factors, it demonstrated the strongest motivation towards ethical investment, where both the countries focused on the sustainability and responsibility towards the environment.

However, both the countries demonstrate ample scope for ethical investments in both the countries and the government of both the countries can play an imperative role to further encourage the motivation towards ethical investments with more awareness on the benefits of the same experienced by both the countries

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